

Digital Marketing Channel and Celebrity Endorsement Analysis of Online Mutual Fund Purchase Decisions with Mutual Fund Performance Mediation

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Abstract:- This study aims to analyze the mediating role of mutual fund performance on digital marketing strategies, namely social media marketing and celebrity endorsements, as well as sales strategies through mobile applications run by investment manager companies, in order to increase mutual fund purchase decisions online in the form of increasing the number of investors and growth mutual fund products. The independent variables are: (1) social media marketing; (2) celebrity endorsements; and (3) mobile applications, while the dependent variable is a mutual fund purchase decision with mutual fund performance as mediation. The population and sample in this study are mutual fund investors who have purchased mutual fund products. This study's population included 123 participants. The SEM-PLS analysis technique is used, and the following research findings are obtained: (1) Social media marketing is not proven to have a positive and significant impact on mutual fund performance; (2) mobile applications are proven to have a positive and significant effect on mutual fund performance; (3) celebrity endorsement is not proven to have a positive and significant impact on mutual fund performance; (4) mutual fund performance has a positive and significant effect on mutual fund purchased decisions online; (5) mutual fund performance does not mediate the relationship between social media marketing and mutual fund purchased decisions online; (6) mutual fund performance mediates the relationship between mobile applications and mutual fund purchase decisions online; (7) mutual fund performance does not mediate the relationship between celebrity endorsement and mutual fund purchase decisions online.

Keywords:- *Mutual Fund Purchased Decision, Online, Digital Marketing, Social Media Marketing, Mobile Application.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In this millennium, capital market activity has developed, driven by the driving force behind alternative investments including stocks, bonds or other securities owned by a group of investors and managed by an Investment Management Company. Among the capital market investment products that are considered ideal by investors because mutual funds have a relatively high return (Rahmah, A., 2016). Mutual funds come from the word

"mutual" which means "to receive" and "funds" which means "money". Referring to the 1995 Capital Market Law, defines Mutual Funds as a means to raise funds from public investors, which are invested by Investment Manager Companies in securities portfolios. As managers of Mutual Fund products, Investment Manager Companies invest their funds in securities and record profits or losses and receive dividends or interest, which are recorded in the Net Asset Value (NAV) of Mutual Funds. NAV is one measure to monitor Mutual Fund Performance.

Today, the Internet has opened the door for Investment Management Companies to take advantage of extraordinary digital marketing opportunities. Digital marketing has been considered as a new marketing method and offers new opportunities for Investment Management Companies which are expected to reach millions of potential Investors buying Mutual Fund products in the next few decades. Digital marketing is simply a marketing activity that is realized through internet and cellular communication, namely on the internet, through social networks, email, apps, platforms, and others (Kannan, P. K., 2017).

Apart from using product marketing through digital marketing, investment management companies can also use the involvement of well-known figures. The involvement of well-known figures such as celebrity endorsements gives the brand an advantage over its competitors and leads to an increase in the company's brand image as well (Misra, K. S., et al., 2019). Aldajani, M.M., and Daajani, M.M. (2019), stated that celebrity endorsements are complicated because they have the potential to increase or weaken an organization's marketing objectives.

Research conducted by Hong, J. Y. (2020) states that developments in digital marketing technology have changed marketing strategies. A new marketing strategy called digital marketing and celebrity endorsement has emerged, and its importance continues to grow. It becomes a challenge for investment management companies to change the direction of a strategy from offline marketing to digital-based marketing.

Based on Table 1, regarding the list of digital platforms for mutual fund selling agents, it is clear that there are currently many technology companies. Informasi yang memilikiaktivitasbagai platform digitaluntukmenjadi APERD.

No	Year of Operation	Brand	Company Name
1	2015	Xdana	PT XdanaInvesta Indonesia
2	2015	Invissee	PT. Nusantara Sejahtera Investama
3	2016	Bareksa	PT Bareksa Portal Investasi
4	2016	Doku	PT Nusa Satu Inti Artha - PT Bareksa Portal Investasi
5	2016	Klik Mami	PT Manulife Aset Manajemen Indonesia
6	2016	Moinves	PT Mandiri Manajemen Investasi
7	2017	BukaReksa	PT Bukalapak.com - PT Bareksa Portal Investasi
8	2017	Investree	PT Investree Radhika Jaya
9	2017	Paypro	PT BNP Paribas Investment Partners
10	2017	TanamDuit	PT Star Mercato Capital
11	2017	TrimaTrimegah	PT Trimegah Securities
12	2017	Bibit	PT BibitTumbuh Bersama
13	2017	Investamart	PT Investamart Principal Optima
14	2018	Moduit	PT Moduit Digital Indonesia
15	2018	Raiz Invest Indonesia	PT Raiz Invest Indonesia
16	2019	Ajaib	PT TakjubTeknologi Indonesia
17	2019	SinarBahana	PT Bahana TCW Investment Management
18	2019	Investasi Kita	PT Nadira Investasi Kita
19	2019	Wahed	PT WahedInvestasi Indonesia
20	2020	Blibli	PT Global Digital Niaga - PT BibitTumbuh Bersama
21	2020	InvestASIK	PT DanareksaInvestmwn Management
22	2020	Ipot Go	PT Indopremier Investment Management
23	2021	Bmoney	PT Buka Investasi Bersama
24	2021	MNC Trade	PT MNC Sekuritas
25	2021	Payuung.com	PT Star Mercato Capitale
26	2021	Pluang	PT BumiSantosaCemerlang
27	2021	Simunvest	PT SinarmasSekuritas
28	2021	Makmur	PT InovasiFinansialTeknologi
29	2021	Panin AM	PT Panin Asset Management
30	2021	PINA	PT Trust Sekuritas
31	2021	Si Jago	PT PNM Investment Management
32	2021	YO! Inves	PT Syailendra Capital
33	2022	SayaKaya	PT Sayakaya Lahir Batin

Table 1: Digital Platforms for Mutual Fund Securities Selling Agents

Source: Processed from www.ojk.go.id, 2022

Based on Figure 1, it can explain the growth of mutual fund investors when investment manager companies have not made many sales through digital platforms and the growth of mutual fund investors when many investment manager companies have made sales through digital platforms. The growth in the number of mutual fund investors for 20 years, from 1996 to 2016, was only 444,945

investors. Meanwhile, the growth of mutual fund investors for seven (seven) years, from 2016 to 2022, was 2,023.73%, or 9,449,438 mutual fund investors, with a digital platform size of around 33 (thirty-three) digital platforms. This expansion was fueled by increased investor interest in mutual fund products and the ease with which mutual fund transactions can be conducted via digital platforms.

Fig. 1: Growth Of Mutual Fund Investors

Source: Processed from www.ojk.go.id, 2022

Based on the background that has been reviewed as well as the significant growth of investors over the past seven (seven) years, the researcher identified the problems to be answered in the results of this study. Identification of these problems and the role of mediation from mutual fund performance to digital marketing strategies, in the form of strategies for social media marketing and mobile applications, as well as sales strategies through celebrity endorsements carried out by investment manager companies in order to increase mutual fund purchase decisions online in the form of increasing the number of investors and growth of mutual fund products, Researchers interested in conducting research entitled "Analysis of Digital Marketing Channels and Celebrity Endorsements on Mutual Fund Purchased Decisions Online with Mutual Fund Performance Mediation"

II. THEORY REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

A. Financial Services Authority

The Financial Services Authority (OJK) is an independent body established under Law Number 21 of 2011. OJK's task is to organize a unified regulatory and control system for all activities in the financial services industry. OJK's task is to regulate and supervise financial services in the banking, capital market, and IKNB sectors.

B. Capital Market

The capital market is a market for various tradable financial instruments, including bonds, shares, mutual funds, derivatives and other instruments. The capital market is a financial and investment vehicle for companies and other institutions (e.g., the government). Thus, the capital market allows various facilities and infrastructure for buying and selling activities and other related activities. Article 8 of Capital Market Law No. 1995 concerning the Capital Market describes the capital market as "activities related to the issuance of public shares and securities trading, public

companies related to the securities they issue, and institutions and professions related to securities."

C. Mutual Fund

Referring to the 1995 Capital Market Law, it defines mutual funds as a means to raise funds from public investors, which are then invested by an investment management company in a securities portfolio. Three things are related to this definition, namely, the source of funds from investors. Second, the fund is invested in a securities portfolio, and third, the fund is managed by an investment management company. Thus, funds from Mutual Funds are shared assets with investors. In general, Mutual Funds are divided into four categories, namely Money Market Mutual Funds, Fixed Income Mutual Funds, Balanced Mutual Funds, and Equity Mutual Funds.

D. Investment Management Company

Based on OJK regulations regarding the implementation of investment portfolio management, it is stipulated that a portfolio manager is a company whose activities include managing securities for the benefit of customers or managing collective investment portfolios for the benefit of customers, except for insurance companies, pension funds, and banks that run their own business based on regulations.

E. Mutual Funds Selling Agent

Mutual Funds Selling Agent (APERD) is a designation for institutions or companies engaged in mutual fund marketing. This can take the form of an investment management company, a bank, a securities company, or—a more recent development—a technology-based financial company, or fintech. With the enactment of the 2014 POJK concerning Mutual Funds Selling Agents and the 2016 OJK Circular Letter concerning Implementation of Mutual Funds Sales at Mutual Funds Sales Outlets, financial technology companies have the opportunity to apply for business licenses as APERD. Financial technology companies can work directly with investment management companies to market mutual fund products.

F. Purchased Decision

Purchased Decision falls under the umbrella of consumer behavior research, which is a vast subject (Tran, H. T., 2020). A purchased decision is a consumer decision regarding the sale of goods or services offered in the market. With the help of digital technology, digital marketing channels such as email marketing, social media, online advertising, and mobile services can improve the consumer's shopping experience at the purchase level by making it easier to order, purchase, and pay for products, saving customers time and money (Qazzafi, S., 2019).

The purchased decision indicator used in this study is based on previous research by Tran, H. T. (2020), which includes:

- Consumers often buy mutual fund products online.
- Consumers feel good when they decide to buy mutual fund products online.
- Consumers intend to buy Mutual Fund products online again in the future.
- Overall, consumers are satisfied with purchasing mutual funds online.

G. Social Media Marketing

Social Media Marketing is a new trend and fast growing way to reach target customers easily and effectively. Social Media Marketing can be easily defined as using social media to promote a company and its products. This type of marketing can be seen as a subset of online marketing activities that complement traditional web-based advertising strategies such as email newsletters and online advertising campaigns (Omar, A., &Atteya., N. 2020). Social Media Marketing is now getting better and more effective insights with the launch of the official social media website platform (Nurunnisha, G. A., et al., 2021).

The Social Media Marketing indicators used in this study are based on previous research by Prasad, S., et al., (2017), which includes:

- Consumer relations with mutual fund products are enhanced by social media.
- Consumers use social media to follow sales and promotions of mutual fund products conducted by investment management companies.
- Investment management companies use social media to contact consumers.
- Consumers use social media to improve relationships with various other mutual fund products.
- Consumers use social media to communicate with investment management companies.

H. Mobile Application

Mobile application is currently the widest, fastest, cheapest, and most up-to-date marketing channel where users can easily obtain information and features of interesting goods and the possibility of completing the buying and selling process without the need for buyers to come to the place. Specifically, mobile applications provide access to consumers to find out their benefits and needs and influence their purchasing decisions (Tiffany, R., et al., 2018). On the other hand, mobile applications are a set of practices that enable organizations to communicate and

interact with their audience in an interactive and relevant manner through any mobile device or network (Mohamed, S., et al., 2016).

The mobile application indicators used in this study are based on previous research by Nabila, E. M. (2021), which includes

- Mobile application assists consumers in the online decision-making process for purchasing mutual fund products.
- Mobile applications can help Mutual Fund products' brand image and brand awareness.
- Mobile applications can keep mutual fund products competitive in the market.
- Mobile application can increase consumer convenience and save time by allowing consumers to purchase mutual funds online.
- Mobile applications can increase the market share of mutual fund products thanks to better network coverage.

I. Celebrity Endorsement

Emphasizing the impact of a celebrity, Aldajani, M.M., and Daajani, M.M. (2019), emphasized that when supporting a brand or product, a celebrity gives the impression that the brand is reliable, and the celebrity's popularity makes people trust the brand. Therefore, Omeregbe, O., and Osifo, S.J. (2019), suggest that companies use more celebrity endorsements to build awareness and perception of their products in the minds of consumers. The effectiveness of celebrity endorsements has been shown in print and television media with increased consumer memory and brand recognition (Castillo-Abdul, B., et al., 2021).

The celebrity endorsement indicator in this study adopts previous research by Misra, K. S., et al. (2019), which includes:

- Very attractive celebrities can incite consumers to buy the mutual fund products they advertise.
- The most effective way of promoting mutual fund products is through celebrity endorsements.
- An advertisement made through celebrity endorsement increases consumers' curiosity about mutual fund products.
- If mutual fund products are advertised by their favorite celebrities, the value of a mutual fund subscription has no effect on consumers.
- Consumers are not affected by the fact that a famous celebrity advertises a mutual fund product.

J. Performance Reksa Dana

According to Syafa'ah, N.L., 2020, mutual funds are a capital market product that is currently in great demand because of the ease of investing. Mutual funds are an investment opportunity for the general public, especially retail investors and investors who do not have the time or expertise to calculate their investment returns. Mutual Fund Performance is a factor that has a significant impact on online mutual fund purchases. This is in accordance with the research of Malik, A. D. (2017). According to (Saputri, W., 2021), investors make very rational decisions when purchasing Mutual Fund products.

The mutual fund performance indicators used in this study are based on previous research by Ng'ang'a, C. M., (2015), which includes:

- The performance of mutual funds can be measured by increasing the yield on mutual fund products.
- Increasing market share will improve mutual fund performance.
- Increasing the mutual fund investor base is one of the criteria for measuring mutual fund performance.

K. Hypothesis Development

What is the mediation role of mutual fund performance on digital marketing strategies, namely social media marketing and mobile applications, as well as sales strategies through celebrity endorsements carried out by investment manager companies in order to increase mutual

fund purchase decisions online, namely in the form of increasing the number of investors and growing mutual fund products? Because the focus of study in this research is mutual fund performance, the mediation test is carried out on 3 independent variables based on previous research, namely the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies on the performance of commercial banks in Kenya (Ng'ang'a, C. M., 2015), the influence of social media promotion strategies on price-mediated purchase decisions (Febriant, R., et al., 2021), and the influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer purchase decisions: A case of Karachi (Khan, A., & Lodhi, S., 2016).

Based on the literature review that has been carried out and the hypotheses that have been compiled, a framework for thinking is created as follows:

Fig. 2: Thinking Framework

Based on the framework above, the conceptual framework of this research is as follows:

- H₁: Social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on mutual fund performance.
- H₂: Mobile applications have a positive and significant effect on mutual fund performance.
- H₃: Celebrity endorsement has a positive and significant effect on mutual fund performance.
- H₄: Mutual fund performance has a positive and significant effect on mutual fund purchase decisions.
- H₅: Mutual Fund Performance serves as a bridge between Social Media Marketing and Online Mutual Fund Purchase Decisions.
- H₆: Mutual Fund Performance mediates the relationship between the mobile application and the online Mutual Fund Purchased Decision.
- H₇: Mutual Fund Performance acts as a go-between for Celebrity Endorsement and Mutual Fund Purchased Decision.

III. METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted to find out how significant the mediation role of Mutual Fund Performance (Z) is on Digital Marketing strategies, namely Social Media Marketing (X₁) and Mobile Application (X₂) as well as sales strategies through Celebrity Endorsements (X₃) run by Investment Manager Companies in order to improve Mutual Fund Purchased Decision (Y) online. The sampling procedure in this study used a non-probability method through a purposive sampling technique. The population and sample in this study consisted of 123 respondents who are Mutual Fund investors who have purchased Mutual Fund products.

The research was conducted in the third quarter or the period from July to September 2022. Primary data collection in this study was obtained directly by filling out the Google Form questionnaire. The distribution of questionnaires was carried out via Google Form which was distributed to several communities where the researcher was a member. Community members who are respondents live in the Jabodetabek area. The list of statements is structured using a Likert Scale of 1-5. The empirical model to test the

hypothesis in this study uses the analytical method through the Partial Least Square (PLS) based Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach. In the Measurement Model (Outer Model), the construct validity and reliability of each indicator are tested. While the Structural Model (Inner Model) uses the t test from the PLS to determine whether there is influence between variables/correlation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Characteristics of respondents

The characteristics of the respondents that have been collected in this study consist of their gender, age, last education, and income.

Category	Group	Respondents	Percentage
		123	100%
Gender	Male	73	59%
	Female	50	41%
Age	<20 years	2	2%
	21 - 30 years	38	31%
	31 - 40 years	36	29%
	> 40 years	47	38%
Last education	High School Graduate	11	9%
	Diploma Graduate	2	2%
	S1 Graduate	86	70%
	S2 Graduate	24	20%
Income per month	< Rp 10 Million	27	22%
	Rp 10 Million- Rp 50 Million	75	61%
	Rp 50 Million- Rp 100 Million	15	12%
	>Rp 101 Million	6	5%

Table 2: Characteristics of Respondents

Source: Questionnaire data processing, 2022

Based on the table of respondents' characteristics, it can be concluded that mutual fund investors who invest in mutual funds online are mostly male investors in the age range of 21–30 years with bachelor's degrees and an income range of Rp. 10–50 million per month. Of course, they are already in a mature state from a financial standpoint and are indeed in the stage of investing for their future, so they can invest in mutual fund products online.

B. Measurement Models

Data processing in this study used the Smart Partial Least Square (SmartPLS) version 3 software as a consideration of the limitations of the sample and research time. In this study, data analysis using SmartPLS was divided into three stages: (1) outer model analysis, which included construct validity and reliability tests and

heterotrait-monotriate ratio of correlations (HTMT) testing; (2) inner model analysis, which includes assessing the value of R-square, f-square, and Q-square and testing the fit model; and (3) hypothesis testing.

➤ *Outer Model*

• **Convergent Validity**

Convergent validity testing is done by testing the loading factor value of each indicator against the construct. The cutoff value used in this study is 0.7. The PLS model is declared convergently validated when the loading factor value is greater than 0.70 and the AVE (average variance extracted) value of each construct is greater than 0.5 (Ghozali, I., and Latan, H., 2015).

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Cutt-Off Value	AVE	Status
Social Media Marketing (SM)	SM 1	0,888	0,7	0,760	Valid
	SM 2	0,887	0,7		Valid
	SM 3	0,895	0,7		Valid
	SM 4	0,846	0,7		Valid
	SM 5	0,826	0,7		Valid
Mobile Application (MA)	MA 1	0,916	0,7	0,772	Valid
	MA 2	0,917	0,7		Valid
	MA 3	0,725	0,7		Valid
	MA 4	0,932	0,7		Valid
	MA 5	0,886	0,7		Valid
Celebrity Endorsement (CE)	CE 1	0,901	0,7	1,000	Valid
	CE 2	0,935	0,7		Valid
	CE 3	0,908	0,7		Valid
	CE 4	0,762	0,7		Valid
	CE 5	0,842	0,7		Valid

<i>Performance Reksa Dana (PR)</i>	PR 2	1,000	0,7	0,853	Valid
<i>Purchased Decision (PD)</i>	PD 1	0,834	0,7	0,755	Valid
	PD 2	0,959	0,7		Valid
	PD 3	0,941	0,7		Valid
	PD 4	0,955	0,7		Valid

Table 3: Convergent Validity Test Results

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2022

• Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity testing is used to ensure that each latent variable is distinct from the others. In this study, the discriminant validity test refers to the Fornell-Larcker criterion test. The results of the Fornell-Larcker criterion

test in the following table show that the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct is greater than the correlation between one construct and the other constructs in the model. The model construct assessed by the AVE score meets the criteria of discriminant validity.

Variable	SM	MA	CE	PR	PD
SM	0,869				
MA	0,775	0,879			
CE	0,686	0,509	0,872		
PR	0,692	0,675	0,592	1,000	
PD	0,714	0,791	0,496	0,579	0,924

Table 4: Fornell-Larcker Discriminant Validity Test

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2022.

• Construct Reability

Construct reliability testing can be seen from the Cronbach alpha value and the composite reliability value of each construct.

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
SM	0,920	0,940	0,760
MA	0,924	0,944	0,772
CE	1,000	1,000	1,000
PR	0,942	0,959	0,853
PD	0,919	0,939	0,755

Table 5: Construct Reliability Test

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2022

The reliability test results in Table 5 above show that all constructs have Cronbach's alpha values > 0.6 and composite reliability > 0.7. This shows that all the constructs or variables in this study have become valid measuring tools, and all the questions used to measure each construct are reliable.

• Heterotrait-Monotriate Ratio Of Correlations (HTMT).

Heterotrait-Monotriate Ratio Of Correlations (HTMT) is the preferred alternative method for assessing discriminant validity. To clearly differentiate these two factors, HTMT must be significantly < 0.9 (Henseler J, et al., 2015). This is due to the view that cross-loading and the Fornell-Larcker criteria are less sensitive in assessing discriminant validity.

Variable	SM	MA	CE	PR	PD
SM					
MA	0,837				
CE	0,747	0,549			
PR	0,719	0,702	0,610		
PD	0,768	0,841	0,537	0,594	

Table 6: Heterotrait-Monotriate Ratio Test Results Of Correlations (HTMT)

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2022

Table 6. The results of the Heterotrait-Monotriate Ratio of Correlations (HTMT) test show that all HTMT values 0.9 indicate that all structures have valid discriminant validity based on HTMT calculations.

➤ Inner Model

• Determinant Coefficient (R²)

The higher the R-squared value, the more independent variables that can explain the dependent variable, so that

the structural equation is better. Based on data processing, the R-squared value is obtained as follows:

Variable	R-square
PR	0,557
PD	0,336

Table 7: R-Squared Test Results

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2022

From Table 7 above it can be seen that the R-squared value of the Mutual Fund Performance variable is 0.557. This R-squared value means that the structural variation of Mutual Fund Performance which can be explained by the structural variation of Social Media Marketing, Mobile Application, and Celebrity Endorsement is 55.7%, while the remaining 44.3% is explained. by other variables. This value indicates the "moderate" category.

Meanwhile, the R-squared value of the Purchased Decision variable is 0.336. This R-squared value means that the variation in the Purchased Decision construct that can be explained by the Mutual Fund Performance construct variation is 33.6%, while the remaining 66.4% is explained by other variables outside the study. This value indicates the "medium" category.

• Effect Size (f^2)

f-square is used to determine whether exogenous latent variables have a significant effect on endogenous latent variables. Based on data processing, the f-Square value is obtained as follows:

Hypothesis	f-square	Effect Size
SM-->PR	0,040	Low
MA -->PR	0,117	Intermediate
CE -->PR	0,006	Low
PR -->PD	0,505	Tall

Table 8: F-Square Test Results

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2022

Based on the results of table 8 regarding the f-square value, it can be stated that the social media marketing variable has a low influence on the mutual fund performance variable. The mobile application variable has a moderate effect on the mutual fund performance variable.

Hypothesis	Path Coefficients	Standard Deviation	t-Statistics	Pvalued	Status
H ₁ SM -> PR	0,250	0,178	1,410	0,159	Not Supported
H ₂ MA -> PR	0,361	0,115	3,136	0,002	Supported
H ₃ CE -> PR	0,236	0,145	1,628	0,104	Not Supported
H ₄ PR -> PD	0,579	0,080	7,208	0,000	Supported

Table 11: Direct Effect Test

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2022

From Table 11, several things are explained as follows:

- **H₁:** The results obtained are t-statistics values of 1.410 < 1.96, P values of 0.159 > 0.05, and path coefficient values of 0.250. These results indicate that social media marketing has not been proven to have a positive and

The celebrity endorsement variable has a low influence on mutual fund performance variables. while the mutual fund performance variable has a high influence on the purchased decision variable.

- Prediction Relevance (Q^2)

If Q-Square > 0 in the structural model, the model has predictive relevance. If Q-Square < 0 then the model is said to have less predictive relevance. Changes in the PLS Q-square value affect the model tested proportionally.

Variable	SSO	SSE	Q2
PR	369.000	162.603	0,559
PD	429.000	272.592	0,365

Table 9: Cross-Validated Redundancy Test Results

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2022

Based on Table 9 regarding the results of the cross-validated redundancy test, it can be explained that the Q-square values are 0.559 and 0.365. Because the Q-square value is greater than 0, the model has predictive relevance.

- Model Fit

The model fit testing phase is about testing the predictive power and feasibility of the model. A research design is considered fit if it shows an SRMR value of 0.09 and if the NFI (Normed Fit Index) is greater than 0.5 or close to 1.

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0,078	0,152
NFI	0,764	0,739

Table 10: Model Fit Test

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2022

From Table 10 above, it can be seen that the SRMR value of 0.152 is less than 0.90, meaning that the model is feasible or meets the model fit criteria. While the NFI value is greater than 0.5, it can be said that the model is feasible or meets the fit model criteria.

➤ Hypothesis Test

Based on the test results, when the path coefficient is positive, the t-statistic is > 1.96, and the P-value is 0.05, the hypothesis is accepted, and it is concluded that exogenous variables have a positive effect on endogenous variables

significant impact on mutual fund performance. The results of this study are not in line with the research of Febrianti, R., et al. (2021).

- **H₂:** The results obtained are t-statistics of 3.136 > 1.96, P-values of 0.002 < 0.05, and a path coefficient

value of 0.361 were obtained. These results indicate that the mobile application has a positive and significant effect on mutual fund performance. The results of this study are in line with previous research from Sivakumar, R., et al. (2020).

- **H3:** The results obtained are t-statistics values of 1.628 > 1.96, P values of 0.104 > 0.05, and a path coefficient value of 0.236. These results indicate that celebrity endorsements have not been proven to have a positive and significant impact on mutual fund

performance. The results of this study are not in line with the research of Hodijah, C., et al. (2021).

- **H4:** The results obtained are t-statistics values of 7.208 > 1.96, P values of 0.000 < 0.05, and path coefficient values of 0.579. These results indicate that mutual fund performance has a positive and significant effect on mutual fund purchase decisions made online. The results of this study are in line with the research of Saputri, W. (2021).

Hipotesis	Path Coefficients	Standard Deviation	t- Statistics	Pvalues	Status	
H5	SM -> PR -> PD	0,145	0,112	1,292	0,197	Not Supported
H6	MA -> PR -> PD	0,209	0,080	2,610	0,009	Supported
H7	CE -> PR -> PD	0,137	0,076	1,796	0,073	Not Supported

Table 12: Indirect Effect Test

Source: Data processed with SmartPLS, 2022

From Table 11, several things are explained as follows:

- **H5:** Based on the mediation hypothesis test, it is known that mutual fund performance does not mediate the relationship between social media marketing and online mutual fund purchases. This is based on the indirect effect test, which produces a P value of 0.197 > 0.05. The results of this study are not in line with the research of Fitria, A. D., &Sijabat, R.,(2021).
- **H6:** According to the results of the mediation hypothesis test in this study, mutual fund performance mediates the relationship between mobile applications and online mutual fund purchases. This is based on the indirect effect test, which has a P value of 0.009 < 0.05. The results of this study are in line with the research of Yusfiarto, R. (2021).

- **H7:** Based on the mediation hypothesis test, it is known that mutual fund performance does not mediate the relationship between celebrity endorsements and online mutual fund purchases. This is based on the indirect effect test, which produces a P value of 0.073 > 0.05. The results of this study are not in line with the research of Bennett, Anaza, and Bennett, D. H., et al. (2021).

C. Pengembangan Model SEM

The theoretical model created in the hypothesis stage is described in the SEM model diagram, which makes it easy to see testable causal relationships. In this diagram, the relationships between constructs are indicated by arrows. Straight arrows indicate a direct causal relationship between one construct and another(Figure 3).

Fig. 3: SEM Model Development output Model PLS

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusions

Based on the output of the analysis and discussion above, conclusions can be drawn, namely:

The research hypothesis (H₁) shows that social media marketing has not been proven to have a positive and significant impact on mutual fund performance. The role of social media marketing in the marketing strategy turns out to be more about the process of literacy and education about mutual fund products. Content posted on social media sites such as Instagram, YouTube, Twitter, Facebook, and others is to invite investors to have brand awareness about mutual fund products that have been managed by investment management companies.

The research hypothesis (H₂) shows that mobile applications have a positive and significant effect on mutual fund performance. The Investment Manager Company must have created a program to have an online mutual fund purchase application system that can be downloaded from an Android or iPhone or cooperate with APERD, which organizes mutual fund sales transactions online. The convenience of prospective investors in transacting through the mobile application will provide many benefits for investment manager companies, namely in the form of increased asset under management, which in turn can improve the performance of mutual fund products.

The research hypothesis (H₃) shows that celebrity endorsements are not proven to have a positive and significant impact on mutual fund performance. The role of celebrity endorsement is more focused on brand awareness of mutual fund products, which cannot be linked to mutual fund performance.

The research hypothesis (H₄) shows that mutual fund performance has a positive and significant effect on mutual fund purchase decisions made online. Investment Manager Companies must pay close attention to the performance of the mutual funds they manage in order for potential investors to be comfortable making purchases of mutual fund products managed by Investment Manager companies.

The research hypothesis (H₅) states that mutual fund performance does not mediate the relationship between social media marketing and mutual fund purchase decisions online. The need for Investment Manager Companies to use social media marketing strategies to promote mutual fund products appears to be only to increase brand awareness so that investors are interested in purchasing mutual funds online.

The research hypothesis (H₆) states that mutual fund performance mediates the relationship between mobile applications and mutual fund purchased decisions made online. Technology in the form of mobile applications has enabled investment management companies to expand their territory to places where they do not have a physical presence. Of course, good mutual fund performance will increase retail mutual fund investors' enthusiasm for making mutual fund purchase decisions through mobile applications.

The research hypothesis (H₇) states that mutual fund performance does not mediate the relationship between celebrity endorsements and mutual fund purchases made online. This hypothesis is unsupported because celebrity endorsements are more geared toward encouraging consumers to purchase mutual fund products than providing a basis for potential mutual fund investors to make purchasing decisions.

B. Suggestion

➤ Theoretical Suggestion

First, future research interested in examining the purchase decision and performance of mutual funds related to digital marketing and celebrity endorsements can re-test the variables in this study by adding or changing some of the variables studied.

Second, future researchers can expand their research objectives not only to global mutual fund products but also to specific mutual fund products based on the type of mutual fund.

Third, increasing the number of research objects can also increase the number of research respondents so that they become more generalized and represent mutual fund investors nationally.

➤ Practical Advice

First, for investment management companies that manage mutual funds, marketing through digital marketing channels must be further strengthened to gain a sizable retail market. The Investment Manager's company strategy needs to strengthen the digital marketing channel, including optimizing the role of the company's website, optimizing the role of social media marketing, and increasing collaboration with APERD Online.

Second, the implementation of literacy and education for retail investors regarding mutual fund products and procedures for conducting mutual fund transactions online must also be increased. Literacy and education can be held through podcasts produced in collaboration with APERD online or by creating educational and literate content that will be posted on investment management companies' social media accounts.

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